

STATE THEORY

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1. INTRODUCTION

The political activity is:

- Free and independent: because it is not subject to any rules, norms or legal norms
- Different: to other activities performed by man
- Self-sufficient: because it is self-sufficient
- Autarkic: because it is governed by its own laws.
- First cause: because it is a generating cause, not only of itself but also of everything else.

This political activity can take place in 4 areas:

- o Micropolitics: refers to face-to-face relationships, power relations are manifested at the individual or group level. Ex. Family, friends, the club
- o Mesopolitics: refers to a slightly broader area at the local or regional level, lower than the nation. It includes the political life of cities and towns.
- o Macropolitics: refers to political activity at the state level (this is the most interesting. Here politics reaches its maximum expression and includes the political relations of national scope that serve to define and explain in depth the entire political life of a country (State)
- o Megapolitics: refers to the level that is given at the international level. This is the existing policy above the nations and is a matter of study of the RRII.

2. POLITICAL DECISIONS

Political decisions will be characterized by a distinctive quality, which are "binding", oblige everyone, to be complied with using the "legitimate force" or "coercion" which is to use, ultimately, legitimately violence to ensure compliance with their decisions.

We can distinguish the Policy as:

- I. Art: It is the personal stamp that each individual imprints on his competence to reach power.
- II. Technique: It is the personal style, but subject to rules, that each ruler imprints on his activity.
- III. Science: is the discipline that is responsible for the systematic and objective knowledge of the facts and phenomena that make up the political reality.

Politics: it is action, act, activity. The political: it is the essence, the power.

Its object of study is the political Reality conformed by:

- facts
- phenomena (the most important is power)

- socialized actors (individual or group)
- dominant (current) ideas, doctrines, ideologies, beliefs, values and opinions
- mediation structures (parties, associations, groups, interest, pressure and tension groups)
- formalized rules for the resolution of conflicts (decrees, regulations, ordinances)
- rules not formalized but implicitly accepted (customary rules)
- institutions (the most important is the state)

This POLITICAL REALITY has certain characteristics:

The political reality unfolds on 2 levels: internal and external. To distinguish them we will consider their determining element: strength. Relationships at the internal level are subordinate and at the external level coordination.

- Internal: it is the political reality that occurs within the political system (State), but without being confused with it, the political precedes and surpasses historically and ontologically the state.
- External: is the political activity that corresponds to the international political system.

The features are:

- It is multiple: the political reality is always the same but it will have multiple manifestations in different historical moments. Ex. A Pharaoh and Menem
- It is multifaceted: within the political reality we will recognize 2 phases:
 - Structural phase: composed of a set of perfectly defined roles, differentiated from each other and hierarchical and to be expressed in institutions. Ex. PE, PL, PJ
 - Dynamic phase: which develops inside the structure. It is carried out by the political actors and their activity can have like immediate aims the occupation of positions or roles in the political system, its conservation, the resistance or the adhesion to the activity that is unfolded of them. As mediated ends we find the realization of a certain representation of a desirable social order. This face in turn comprises:
 - Agonal phase: it is oriented towards the immediate end of political activity, to reach power. It implies competition for power among those who want to hold government positions. Menem 98: agonal (because his term was coming to an end and he didn't want to lose it)
 - Architectural phase: it is the exercise of political power by the rulers and in general is oriented towards the mediated ends, guarantee coexistence and the common good, that is, achieve a desirable social order. It is therefore the creative, constructive, conductive and integrating activity. Ex. Menem 96
 - Plenary phase: it is the integration of the 2 previous ones (agonal + architectural). The plenary phase looks for the balance between the consensus and the conflict, between order and movement and between stability and change. Ex. The political activity of every day.
- It is variable: we will always find those 3 previous phases, in time the modalities in which they appear vary, because the forms, the activities, the behaviors, the beliefs and the dominant values of a political community vary
- It is symbolic: it is a symbolic reality, the political reality is not objective like nature, nor subjective like dreams, but it is objectifiable, impregnated with the subjectivism of men. Symbols are present in political reality
- It is multi-related: it will maintain relationships with all other manifestations of human reality, with society, with morality, with the economy, law, etc.

In order for these elements to be qualified as politicians they must be inserted in some of the categories of the political thing: (FREUND)

In the relationship I command obedience: politics is understood as an interhuman relationship in which the action of some determines the behavior of others. This budget is clearly political in its two terms: command and obedience. And also because from this relationship emerges the specific means of politics, the "force", whose monopoly is centralized by the state,

The public and the private: the public sphere is characterized by relations of subordination between rulers and ruled, unequal relations that materialize through the law (society as a whole); while in private these relations are of coordination, between equals and materialize by means of the contract. (each of us as members of society)

Friend - enemy: maintains that the politician can find his strength in various sectors of human life, not indicating a particular sector, but the degree of intensity, creating the dialectic of conflict and struggle with the public enemy. They occur in international relations when my interests coincide with those of another state, a condition in which he will be my "friend," and when interests come into conflict, that state will be my "enemy."

"As the political is in some way conditioned by the social, any fact or phenomenon, not essentially political can have political impact, even natural facts and phenomena. Under normal conditions the first 2 categories are internally and the third in the external. In abnormal conditions the 3rd category friend - enemy enters the internal plane. "

STATE

The state is a political community and as such can be distinguished in two ways:

- State in the broadest sense: when we refer to any political community that has existed, exists or will exist. In a broad sense, it existed from the dissolution of the primitive community, based on kinship ties, which motivated the formation of larger communities derived from the union of many family groups for reasons of internal survival and external defense.

Horde. Family. Clan (union of families with mythical cohesion) Phratry (several clans) Tribes. Village. City. City-State. Nations. States

- State in the strict sense: a political form of coexistence that makes its appearance in the modern age resulting from the process of institutionalization of power (Modern State)

Birth of the Modern State (13th and 14th centuries)

When the Greek polis loses its splendor, the center of civilization moves to Rome, whose forms of organization are called first Civitas, then Republic and finally Empire.

In the Middle Ages, civilization settled on the shores of the Mediterranean. Then come the barbarian invasions, which causes the isolation of cities, so power is being privatized. The Emperor was no longer so influential, but he was the Feudal Lord. This situation lasted until the twelfth century, when trade routes were protected from Venice. The feudal lords declared themselves sovereign, and exercised power within their lands, this is the emergence of the Modern State. The Modern State had to fight against different forms of organization in order to grow and settle. Once he managed to defeat them, the state became established as a form of political organization:

- Empire
- Feudal Lords
- Papacy

In primitive societies power was anonymous (family authority, priest, tribal chief, sorcerer, etc.); over time it is transformed into personalized power (communities decide to obey a leader or leader, who is awarded extraordinary qualities), but the problem arises when that leader dies, there is usually a bloody struggle for succession; the man then realizes that it is bad to obey another man, decides to depersonalize power, being now institutionalized (he will obey an institution that he himself creates, and which he calls State)

The state will then be the seat of political power.

State

- According to George Jellinek, "where there is a community based on a territory, with original power and coercive means to rule over its members and territories, according to its own order, there is a STATE."

- From this definition of state, arise the elements that make it up:
- Territory

- Population (human element)
- Power (original power: the will of a people to form a state)
- 1- TERRITORY
- It is the physical environment where the state develops its activity. Three aspects about the Territory:
 - From the political point of view: the state exercises sovereignty over its territory, only the authorities of that state will dominate over that territory. The scope of territorial sovereignty is exercised over all persons who are in the territory of the State whether inhabitants, tourists or travelers and includes the things and legal consequences of events in the territory of the state, but has limitations such as the right private international law or public international law.
 - From the geographical point of view: the state is framed within its limits: which are continuous, natural or artificial lines that -as an ideal entity- separate one sovereign state from another. (Borders are contact areas of 2 or more states in the extent of their common boundaries)
 - From the legal point of view: the territory is the spatial scope of validity of the rules.
- The territory includes: the land surface, the maritime space and the airspace
- **Espacio Terrestre:** parte de la superficie de la tierra enmarcada dentro de los límites. Comprende:
 - Suelo: la superficie de la tierra, ríos, aguas interiores, puertos, radas, bahías, ríos, lagos y mares interiores.
 - Subsuelo: lo que está debajo del suelo, los límites se proyectan hasta converger en el *centro de la tierra*.
- **Espacio Marítimo:** comprende:
 - Mar territorial: cuando un estado posee un litoral marítimo se le reconoce una franja costera denominada "mar territorial". Si bien no hay acuerdo sobre la extensión de dicha zona, prevalece internacionalmente: **12 millas marinas** (antiguamente era calculado por el alcance de las balas del cañón. Y desde las costas hasta las **200 millas** se denomina "Zona Económica Exclusiva" (el Estado ejerce sólo jurisdicción), tiene derecho de hacer uso de los recursos naturales.
 - Plataforma continental: nosotros reivindicamos la "plataforma marítima", es la prolongación submarina del territorio continental, comprendiendo el lecho del mar y el subsuelo mas allá del mar continental hasta los **200 metros** de profundidad.
- Airspace: is the mass of air or atmospheric space, the boundaries are projected perpendicular to the stratosphere (begins when the earth begins to exert gravity. What is outside the stratosphere, outer space, in 1967 was declared " common thing of humanity "(res communis humanitatis)
- * Therefore: the upper limit of the state is the stratosphere and the lower, the center of the earth.

POPULATION

- It is the total number of inhabitants living in a state (whether natives or foreigners residing in it). All inhabitants enjoy civil rights. The population can be studied in its various aspects:
 - Quantity: politics is interested in the number of people who make up its human element.
 - Density: is the relationship between the number of inhabitants and the Km²
 - Distribution by age: it is a recordable data with little margin of error that is plotted using the population pyramid.
 - To study its quantitative aspects this is the demography (use the Census, the population pyramid, the density of hab./km²)
 - Quality: it will tell us if the populations are homogeneous or heterogeneous according to race, nationality, religion, education, economic resources, etc.
 - To study its qualitative aspect is demology (mortality rate, birth rate, masculinity rate, etc.
- Within the population element there are two concepts: NATION AND PEOPLE

- • Nation: (Ernest Renán) is the set of men who share common glories in the past, a common project in the present, having done great things together and still want to do them. The Nation is a feeling of belonging to a certain community (subjective elements), sharing language, race and religion (objective elements) Communities, once they establish their identity as a nation, seek to transform into a state, the nation pre-exists the state, you can try to do it the other way around, but it is more complicated) There may be states that are not nations Ex. (Former Yugoslavia) and non-state nations (gypsies or Jews until 1948 with Israel).
- The Nation lacks "power," the formal and specific organization. It has no headquarters or institutional form, it has no government, it is not organized, nor can it be inhabited, it is just a social group. Not the entire population is part of the nation, only those that share the subjective and objective elements. (In our constitution the term nation is equivalent to that of state)
- People: it is an organized political community in the State, that is, with the capacity to govern itself fully. It will be a part of the population, the general population will enjoy civil rights, the people in addition to civilians will enjoy political rights (choose and be elected) = citizens. To be a citizen in this country there are requirements (to be over 18 years old, to be a native or naturalized Argentine. The population becomes a people when it becomes a political community. Then it will be the people who legitimize the power of domination as a power of authority.

PODER (State)

It is the relationship of command-obedience, between rulers and ruled.

Characteristics of the State Power:

- It is an institutionalized power: settled in an institution (State), depersonalized, stabilized, structured, organized and oriented towards the public good, above particular interests. Organized because it regulates succession and participation in power. It exerts its action on the same men who have established it.
- It is a power of domination: because it is an irresistible power that has the means of coercion to ensure obedience throughout the spatial and personal sphere of the state. According to Weber, to dominate is to obtain obedience to a specific mandate.
- It is a coercive power: because it has the monopoly of force or legitimate violence (coercion. This monopoly is what has distinguished the modern state from other historical political forms.

State power is also distinguished by an essential quality: sovereignty, which expresses state supremacy - is sovereign, does not recognize any other power above it. This sovereignty will materialize mainly in the dictation of laws through the congress or parliament, to apply those laws through the judges and to execute the orders of government through the bureaucratic apparatus of the public administration. The state as a legislator is irreproachable, as an irresistible execution and as an unappealable judge. To exercise this power will use the coercion and consent of the inhabitants. Coercion implies an imperative domination between rulers and ruled. Consent consists in generating the acceptance of the governed in being guided towards a goal. To the extent that you have less consent, you will have more need to use force (autocracies), the other way around when it is very legitimate (democracies)

Power Relationship:

- Command: If the power is exercised in accordance with the law, that power will be legal.
- Obedience: if the ruled think that the ruler has the right title to rule it is said that power is legitimate.

The determination of the fairness or otherwise of such titles will depend on the dominant beliefs and values.

3. CONCLUSIONS

The first state was absolute (theorized by Hobbes. Then it became liberal by the French Revolution, whose goal was to limit the power of Locke, Montesquieu), this liberal state recognizes the civil rights of citizens.

Over time, the problem of ownership of power is raised, there is a great impact on the world by the Industrial Revolution, people move to cities, who demand more participation, and this leads to universal suffrage. The state becomes a liberal democracy, where political rights are recognized. Then this state is transformed into a liberal democratic state governed by

the rule of law, and is characterized by the rule of law. Finally, it evolves into a welfare state or welfare state (originated from the crisis of 29), which adds social rights (health, education, etc.), which are guaranteed by the state. This welfare state enters a crisis in 1973 with the oil problem, the Arab countries join forces in OPEC and decide to increase its price, thus increasing the spending of the buyer countries and the crisis begins. And it is this same crisis that is causing external debt in underdeveloped countries.

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